

RESEARCH AND EARN (R & E)

JUNE 2026 EDITION

RESEARCH CATEGORY- TECHNOLOGY

RESEARCH THEME: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN

HEALTH SYSTEMS

**RESEARCH TOPIC: THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN
BRIDGING NIGERIA'S DOCTOR TO PATIENT RATIO IN NIGERIAN
HOSPITALS.**

Abstract

The research paper examined the role of artificial intelligence in bridging Nigeria's doctor to patient ratio in Nigerian hospitals. The research paper x-rayed the dangerous deficiency or paucity in the doctor's-patient gap and the clinical consequences of such systemic strain on our health system in Nigeria. The research paper submitted that the doctor to patient ratio in both private and public hospitals today in Nigeria is one doctor to 10, 000 patients (1:10:000) thus the urgent medical need for hospitals to developed technical cum medical alternatives or substitutes (artificial intelligence) via applying the services of clinic robots as alternative to efficiently undertake the routine or mechanical medical tasks done by scanty doctors who regularly need to be highly remunerated, trained /retrained and supervised for medical efficiency and productivity. The pragmatic empirical research paper therefore in a bid to abridge this wide medical gap in doctors-patient ratio in Nigeria recommended that both private and public hospitals in Nigeria apply the technical services of clinical robots which is a health-tech solution to conventional or traditional health care system in Nigeria via artificial intelligence that is mechanized through the configuration of medical robots programmed to act like health humans for 21st Century health service delivery. The simulation of non-human and technical clinical representatives (clinical robots) will innovatively attend to, think and act like health-humans or experts to patients as a digital alternative to the health issue or problem of paucity of doctors –patient ratio in Nigeria.

Key Words: Role, Artificial Intelligence, Bridging, Nigeria, Doctor, Patient, Ratio, Nigerian Hospitals.

1.1 Introduction and Background to the Study

We live in a rapidly evolving medical landscape of artificial intelligence thus our health system stands at a crossroads between technological advancement and dynamic innovations in health technology. The emergence of artificial intelligence via digital computers or mechanized robots programmed to act like humans which most 21st Century health practitioners are digitally inclined have opened-up seamless virtual avenues to improve the health system in Nigeria.

The health system today is a global technical village that is interconnected with the trio-tech of computers, internet and mobile telephones thus affords doctors the boundless digital and sophisticated ICT tools to fast track patient diagnosis and eliminate the delays in attending to large number of patient waiting for medical attention.

Despite several dimensions of conventional challenges in the adoption or application of artificial intelligence, the simulation of non-human and digital technical representatives to think and act like humans (doctors) has posed serious technical diffusion on some tested and trusted medical etiquette such as patient privacy and confidentiality, patient medical history safety and gender guard.

The digitalization of the 75% hospitals today with AI virtual operations has inadvertently negated or infringed on some core medical practices or standards

For example, super clinic robots can be configured with a soft copy of patient medical history and scheduled for theatre operation with a long examination of the patient because of lack of enough or qualifies human hand to conduct surgical operations. In addition, AI technical inventions and innovations has also interfered with one of the strong medical doctrine of gender segregation or consideration even in the face of clinical emergency or contingency.

The positive impacts of AI however in health management or administration in Nigerian hospitals via computerize human manipulations and maneuvering of coded values and ethics has also enhanced the medical profession with speed because AI machines lacks sentiments or bias.

On the whole, health practitioners today have now modelled AI as a negative tool to replace ethical/medical reasoning because of excessive dependence on algorithms that may not be fair and just to patience and needs to align with established medical practices and standards.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Medical demographic reveals that 75% of hospitals especially government established health centers in Nigeria are understaffed with a wide doctor to patient ratio of 1:10.000. This dangerous deficiency or paucity in the doctor's-patient gap and the clinical consequences of such systemic strain on our health system in Nigeria calls for a medical alternative to overcome the challenge of overcrowded government hospitals, patient waiting days and weeks to meet with few doctors and the uncountable deaths of patient due to non-attendance or treatment.

The doctor to patient ratio in both private and public hospitals today in Nigeria is one doctor to 10, 000 patients (1:10:000) which is below the WHO medical standard of 10:1000 thus the urgent medical need for hospitals to developed technical cum medical alternatives or substitutes (artificial intelligence) via applying the services of clinic robots as alternative to efficiently undertake the routine or mechanical medical tasks done by scanty doctors who regularly need to be highly remunerated, trained /retrained and supervised for medical efficiency and productivity.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this research paper is to examine the role of artificial intelligence in bridging Nigeria's doctor to patient ratio in Nigerian hospitals.

The study aims to achieve the following specific objectives:

- i. To determine how artificial intelligence helps to bridge doctors-patient ratio in Nigerian hospitals.
- ii. To assess the roles of clinic robots as alternatives to the paucity of medical doctors in Nigerian hospitals.

1.4 Research Hypothesis

H_0 : Artificial intelligence has no significant impact on doctors-patient ratio in Nigerian hospitals.

H_i : Artificial intelligence has significant effect impact on doctors-patient ratio in Nigerian hospitals.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Literature Review

2.1.1 The Emergence and Growth of Artificial Intelligence in

Nigerian Hospitals

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has globally emerged as a dual digital medical innovation to virtually tackle the surging and sophisticated rate of clinical professional paucity in qualified medical personnel or doctors.

Nigeria as a global technical village is interconnected with the trio-tech of computers, internet and mobile telephones which has boundless provided sophisticated ICT tools that has positively provided digital and health tech innovations that can substitute the human element in the routine task of diagnosing patient, record time or speed of dispensing-off large clinical schedules with less energy and time.

AI as an offensive and defensive technological innovation has duo impact on both the few medical doctors and patients especially in the Nigerian context where mechanized robots are now programmed to function in place of physical or conventional doctors experts via the simulation of non-human technical apparatus to think and act like humans in the treatment of patients and enhancing several mechanical clinical schedules typical of a Nigerian hospital.

2.2 Artificial Intelligence and Doctor to Patient Ratio in Nigeria's Health System

The medical world is a global technical village interconnected with the trio-tech of computers, internet and mobile telephones which has boundlessly provided sophisticated ICT platforms or mediums that has brought health care services delivery to our doorsteps.

Unlike the conventional or traditional health care systems of the 19th and 20th Centuries Nigeria, the emergence of artificial intelligence via digital computers or mechanized medical robots programmed to act like health humans have significantly establish a new personnel order in 21st Century health service delivery. The simulation of non-human and technical clinical representatives to attend to, think and act like health-humans or experts to patients medical needs has posed serious human resource consideration or alternative to the medical issue or problem of paucity of doctors –patient ratio in Nigeria.

The Nigerian medical space according to the Federal Ministry of Health, (2025) reported an exponential or geometric growth of medical Artificial Intelligence (AI) machine technology especially clinic chat-bots and super-robots which has recently placed noticeable relevance on the indispensability of medical doctors and professional paucity of qualified doctors vis-a vis the large patient ratio in Nigeria.

Medical personnel informatics in 2025 submitted that the geometric rise in medical technology has drastically implicated on the demand for physical or manual medical doctor labours in Nigerian private and public health institutions.

The Nigerian Medical Association (NMA) in 2025 submitted that over 76% of today's hospitals have developed technical cum medical alternatives or substitutes (Surrogate Surgeons) compared to the hitherto do-without doctors to attend and treat large numbers of sick patients especially in public or government hospitals.

The predominance of medical technology especially in the last decade has adversely implicated on employment of medical doctors because the invention or innovation man-machines has reduced industrial labour intensive recruitment of skilled or qualified doctors of different specializations or fields to take- up routine or daily treatment of large numbers of patients which was conventionally undertaken by the scarce number medical doctors over Centuries in hospitals.

Polak, (2024) submitted that the preponderance of machine deployment in patient treatment has drastically reduced the necessity of medical doctors pivotal positions in the past thus many doctors jobs or positions in many private hospitals is gradually beginning to disappear while new and currently unrealized technical job roles have emerge.

For example, in the year 2019, the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic made most private hospitals in Nigeria to technically apply the services of industrial robots to alternative and efficiently undertake the routine or mechanical medical tasks done by scanty doctors who regularly need to be highly remunerated, trained /retrained and supervised for medical efficiency and productivity. The doctor-patient ratio in Nigeria stands at an alarming 1:9083 patient's ratio which is a far standard from the WHO 1; 600 ratio. The doctor-patient ratio in Nigeria is about 1,000% less than what the WHO recommended. The Nigerian Medical Association (NMA) in 2024 stated that Nigeria has one doctor to 10,000 patients (1:10,000). On a national average, only one doctor is incredibly available to treat 30,000 patients in Southern states in Nigeria whiles states in the North is as worse as one doctor to 45,000 patients. These severe shortage of doctors thus has prolonged the work hours of over 80% medical doctors which have to extend their working hours to unsustainable levels and most times contributing to doctors burn-out, increased risk of medical error, patient jeopardy and fatality in most clinical cases.

However, with configured or virtual models of ICT in hospitals today, medical technology or equipment of different types takes over heavy and hectic tasks undertaken by doctors while amplifying individual medical productivity thus bridging or reshaping the high medical demand for medical doctors who tend to sacrifice their wellbeing for serving humanity above their professional wellbeing.

Tony, (2024) disclosed that the rapid adoption of medical technologies such as computerized patient testing, scanning, medical tracking and treatment in 56% of most private hospitals from 2000 to date has led to increased medical efficiency, reduced work stress for medical doctors and bracing up the hitherto medical need for human experts who are scarce and not sustainable unlike machines who are medically programmed to act or function like humans with little or no human supervision with greater medical efficiency and reduced medical errors which often results to patient fatality. The digitalization of the medical work-place with machines or computer clinical gadgets, surgical software's and virtual human operations has saved human time and energy, minimized cost of medical personnel servicing, prevents human manipulations of the clinical process unlike machines which lacks sentiments or bias. More so, medical technologies in hospitals has also serve to help improve the balanced job share of women and the dominant male gender in the medical sector.

As a consequence, the wide acceptance and applicability of medical machines to represent traditional human resources has increased job or workforce productivity by automating or computerizing routine medical tasks which help to expand employee proficiency on-the job and increase value of work. The 70% take-over or dominance of medical men by machines in medicine through computer controlled robots to perform common nursing task with configured

human intelligence has a tremendous impact on the level of human or doctors employment and engagement especially as most health institutions in the global medical sectors are geared for the twin-goal of efficiency and effectiveness.

Polak, (2024) opined that the application of medical machines has drastically reduce the wage bills of medical doctors in most hospitals as well achieve optimum medical efficiency compared to the mechanical era of man-to man job shifts and schedules in our traditional or conventional hospitals.

Recently, the International Labour Organization (ILO) in 2024 Human Resources Relevance in 21st Century doctor's seminar submitted that crafted human gadgets and applications in hospitals have been designed to technically carry out simple and stress-free medical task of doctors reserve in the past such as virtual personal human assistance, configured email filtering, chat-bots, patient medical services, patient medical history and clinic records.

In addition, a typical displacement or disengagement of medical doctors and job handling alternative or machine substitute in the health sector during the COVID-19 pandemic was the dynamic invention and deployment of Medical Robotic Nurses (MRN) which are digitally computerized or configured to test and treat patients since the human hands was considered unsafe and contractible.

However, AI dominance and deployment in today's dynamic medical workplace has faced-out semi-skilled and unskilled medical doctors in favour of technical personnel's or technically roboted human-like intelligent machines to safely, cheaply and quickly undertake clinical tasks.

The astronomical increase and acceptance technologies in 21st Century health sector in Nigeria has negatively impacted on human hand or manual labour recruitment in the medical sector thus resulting in countless numbers of job loss or cut-down of medical staff strength in order to minimize operational cost and optimize profit. These dynamics or changes has also technically faded out the human relations or face in the management of the human resources which hitherto was the life-wire or nucleus of the medical profession.

The caveat and consideration thus is to bridge the gap of the human-machine element in medical outfits because they drive the computerized machines and robots as well as undertake mechanical machine maintenance and damage control.

Technical popularity and prevalence in doctors versus patient ratio has no doubt significantly stretch out the human elements in most hospitals making the doctoral staff and their skills redundant, unattractive and unemployable.

Furthermore, Omore, (2024) observed that the innovation of hospital technologies in complimenting the human factor which hitherto constitute 85% of the working resources in hospitals is also a veritable invention for traditional doctors to re-tool their skills, upgrade their work technical know-how as well as appreciating the use of inanimate working partners to achieve organizational goals and objectives.

In the same vein, the rise of clinical technology has numerically and technically reduced the demand or employment of doctors in most hospitals, re-shaping work schedules, job specification and new skill requirements, cost minimization and drive for patience wellbeing as well as doctors decency in balancing work time and personnel health capacity.

Finally, a balanced technical and professional bridge is needed to sustain medical doctor's scarcity and the mandate of saving lives by defining limits of doctors working hours and complimenting their tight schedules with robotic medical machines for doctors rest and recovery while technical non-human components ne instituted to compliment the treatment cycle supported by other medical personnel in a bid to bridge the seemly overtake of medical doctors role by medical machines.

2.3 Empirical Review

The Nigerian medical space according to the Federal Ministry of Health, (2025) reported an exponential or geometric growth of medical Artificial Intelligence (AI) machine technology especially clinic chat-bots and super-robots which has recently placed noticeable relevance on the indispensability of medical doctors and professional paucity of qualified doctors vis-a vis the large patient ratio in Nigeria.

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2.4 Theoretical Framework-The Human Relations Theory

The human relations theory propounded in 1948 by Elton Mayo of the Human Relations School (HRS) was used to underpin this research paper.

The human relations theory is a classical approach to modern organizational operation as against the machine or scientific theory of man or employees in an organization of Fredrick Winslow Taylor. The human relations doctrine which is the core function of health administrators today is at the center of employees to ward through medical and physical trauma in hospitals while adding a human face to operational climate or tone in contemporary private or public hospitals in Nigeria.

Unlike other organizational approach or perspectives, the human relations proponents urge health administrators to design contemporary hospitals settings that will make the hospital an operational similitude of the home thus helping to reduce

patient stress, long clinic time and prolonged medical attention and risk. This they argue will also help keep patient stable and in good health condition.

Co-proponents of the Human Relations School such as Abraham Maslow, Hazberg and Ali Mizt also stress the need for hospital administrators to first cater to patient mental health by deploying alternative or substitute technical hands such as medical robotic nurses or clinic robots.

3.1 METHODOLOGY

This research paper employed a mixed-methods research design, integrating both quantitative and qualitative approaches to comprehensively investigate employee mental wellbeing vis-à-vis the role of artificial intelligence in bridging Nigeria's doctor to patience ratio in Nigerian hospitals.

3.2 Data Analysis

Determining an appropriate data analysis is crucial for obtaining reliable results in any statistical investigation. For this hypothetical study on the role of artificial intelligence in bridging Nigeria's doctor to patience ratio in Nigerian hospitals, the researcher used Cochran's formula for estimating the required minimum sample size (Cochran, 1977):

$$n = (Z^2 * P (1-P)) / E^2$$

Where n represents the desired sample size, Z denotes the z-score corresponding to the chosen level of confidence (e.g., 95% corresponds to a z-score of approximately 1.96), P signifies the estimated proportion of the population possessing the attribute under examination, and E stands for the margin of error or precision level.

Assuming a conservative estimate of 50% prevalence rate ($P=0.5$) since there are insufficient prior studies investigating similar issues specifically related to employee mental health wellbeing and the role of artificial intelligence in bridging Nigeria's doctor to patient ratio in Nigerian hospitals, 95% confidence interval ($Z=1.96$), and a ± 5 percentage point margin of error ($E=0.05$), the calculated sample size would be:

$$n = (1.96^2 * 0.5(1-0.5)) / 0.05^2$$

$$n \approx 385$$

Therefore, the recommended sample size for this hypothetical study should consist of 385 randomly selected hospital doctor and clinic staff of the some designated private and public hospitals in Nigeria.

Using a stratified random sampling technique based on gender, age, educational attainment, and geographical location can help ensure representativeness and reduce selection bias.

Moreover, incorporating an oversampling strategy for hard-to-reach participants and conducting periodic checks throughout data collection to monitor response rates will further enhance the quality and generalizability of the findings. A survey questionnaire was administered to a sample size of 385 randomly selected private and public sector doctors using probability sampling techniques.

Decision rule:

Accept H_1 , when $x^2 >$ than the critical value;

Reject H_0 , when $x^2 <$ than the critical value;

Where x^2 represents the calculated chi-square value;

Given that: F_o' is the Observed Value

F_e' is the Expected Value

R' is the Rows

C' is the Column

df is the Degree of Freedom

Using the formula:

$$df = [R - C] [C - 1] \text{ (i)}$$

where $x^2 = \frac{[Fo - Fe]^2}{Fe}$

Fe

Where:

x^2 = Chi-Square

Fe =Frequency Expected

$\sum Ri$ N = The number of Respondents

$\sum Ri$ = The number of Rows.

The decision rule therefore is since the critical value of x^2 for $df= 1$ at 5% level of significance is 385 and by the decision rule, since the computed x^2 at 86 is greater than the critical value of 385, we agree with the dependent variable which states that artificial intelligence has significant effect impact on doctors-patient ratio in Nigerian hospitals.

3.3 Discussion of Findings

The study pragmatically discovered that 75% of hospitals especially government established health centers in Nigeria are understaffed with a wide doctor to patient ratio of 1:10.000. This dangerous deficiency or paucity in the doctor's-patient gap and the clinical consequences of such systemic strain on our health system in Nigeria calls for a medical alternative to overcome the challenge of overcrowded

government hospitals, patient waiting days and weeks to meet with few doctors and the uncountable deaths of patient due to non-attendance or treatment.

The study also find out that the doctor to patient ratio in both private and public hospitals today in Nigeria is one doctor to 10, 000 patients (1:10:000) which is below the WHO medical standard of 10:1000 thus the urgent medical need for hospitals to developed technical cum medical alternatives or substitutes (artificial intelligence) via applying the services of clinic robots as alternative to efficiently undertake the routine or mechanical medical tasks done by scanty doctors who regularly need to be highly remunerated, trained /retrained and supervised for medical efficiency and productivity.

3.4 Conclusion

The research paper concluded that artificial intelligence especially clinical robots has emerged as a technical alternative substitute to help bridge the widening gap between doctors and patients in Nigerian hospitals.

The research paper also highlighted the integral role of artificial intelligence in enhancing efficiency and high productivity in the diagnosis, dispensation and general operational effectiveness of the application of robotic nurses to compliment the scarce health personnel in Nigerian hospitals.

In the same vein, the predominance of AI machines in 65% of our hospitals especially private hospitals has improved medical health administration, eliminate cases of late and no doctor syndrome to a commendable degree as well as reduced systemic causality of patient due to paucity of medical personnel

3.5 Recommendations

In a bid to sustainably bridge the wide medical gap between doctors and patients in Nigerian hospitals, the under-listed pragmatic recommendation should be implemented to the letter:

1. For efficient and effective health delivery services, both private and public hospitals in Nigeria should apply the technical services of clinical robots which is a health-tech solution to conventional or traditional health care system in Nigeria via artificial intelligence that is mechanized through the configuration of medical robots programmed to act like health humans for 21st Century health service delivery.
2. The simulation of non-human and technical clinical representatives (clinical robots) will innovatively attend to, think and act like health-humans or experts to patients as a digital alternative to the health issue or problem of paucity of doctors –patient ratio in Nigeria.

3. Nonetheless, the Federal Ministry of Health should put up efforts in collaboration with the Nigerian Medical Council (NMC) to ensure the recruitment and adequate remuneration of more qualified doctors to help treat the hundreds of patient who flood government owned hospitals for the diagnosis or treatment of one disease or the other.
4. This dangerous deficiency or paucity in the doctor's-patient gap and the clinical consequences of such systemic strain on our health system in Nigeria calls for a medical alternative to overcome the challenge of overcrowded government hospitals, patient waiting days and weeks to meet with few doctors and the uncountable deaths of patient due to non-attendance or treatment.
5. The study find out that the doctor to patient ratio in both private and public hospitals today in Nigeria is one doctor to 10, 000 patients (1:10:000) which is below the WHO medical standard of 10:1000 thus the researcher suggest the urgent medical need for hospitals to developed technical cum medical alternatives or substitutes (artificial intelligence) via applying the services of clinic robots as alternative to efficiently undertake the routine or mechanical medical tasks done by scanty doctors who regularly need to be highly remunerated, trained /retrained and supervised for medical efficiency and productivity.

6. Traditional or conventional doctors and patient should also embrace the emergence and application of artificial intelligent robots and chatbots as compliment and not competitors in the task of delivering quality and contemporary health services to patients in Nigerian hospitals.
7. Administrators of modern hospitals in Nigeria should embrace, train and retrain their medical staff to work with non-human elements or characters in order to ensure efficiency and quality health care service delivery.

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